

INCORPORATING DANCE MOVEMENT THERAPY AS A PREVENTIVE AND COMPLEMENTARY TREATMENT IN INDIAN HOSPITALS

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Introduction

Health is primarily defined as a ‘state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not the absence of disease or infirmity’. It is also the ability to adapt and manage oneself in the face of social, physical and emotional challenges. Health and fitness is generally an outcome of a combination of factors – those being appropriate exercise for the mind and body, balanced diet and genetics. Apart from these, dance is also known to have a significant impact on mental, physical and social health of an individual.

Dance is something which has been in practice since ages and is a part of spiritualism as well as celebrations. Festivals, victories and joyous occasions – all had dance as a part of celebration. Folk, classical, semi-classical, tribal or even modern or contemporary forms of dancing are all an inherent aspect of life in varying degrees world over.

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Today Dance Movement Therapy (DMT) is used in hospitals as well as at comprehensive clinical cancer centres in the western world. While in countries like India, though Dance Movement Therapy is well-recognized as a complementary psychotherapeutic line of treating patients of Alzheimer's, Dementia, Fibromyalgia, Cancer, Parkinson's, Depression, anxiety and many more, it still needs to be formally included in the services and facilities provided in the hospitals.

Dance per se, is an artistic expression through rhythmic movement to music. It uniquely combines social, cognitive and fitness components. There are innumerable benefits of dance in terms of physical, social and mental health. Dance also helps in creating mindfulness and alleviates stress and brings a sense of joy and calm to the individual. As far as physical health is concerned, dance may be beneficial in improving muscular strength, endurance, balance, cardiovascular fitness, postural stability etc. Dance can also help in initiating brain plasticity mechanism to a great extent. In the context of Indian classical dances such as Kathak, Bharatnatyam, Odissi, Kuchipudi and others; the numerous hasta mudras(hand gestures) and the intricate footwork serve in activating different acupressure points and physiological processes. This in turn, helps in keeping strengthening

internal organs and keeping one fit and healthy.

Aim of the Study

Dance Movement Therapy is based on the principle that movement reflects an individual's pattern of thinking and feeling. It emphasizes that human body through its primary means of communication and expression may offer a possibility to work through issues that are difficult to articulate because they are painful, frightening or simply difficulty to access and address through cognitive means.

Therefore, this study aims to review the related literature in order to determine the feasibility of incorporating DMT as a preventive and supplementary line of therapy in Indian hospitals.

Methodology

Methodology includes reviewing of related literature from several Indian and International sources. A content analysis is undertaken to determine the feasibility of incorporating DMT as a preventive and supplementary line of therapy in Indian hospitals. Research Journals based on studies undertaken in the field of Medicine and Dance have been accessed to analyze related literature.

Apart from this some empirical data has been collected so as to add credibility to the current study and the recommendations. The sample size is small due to constraint of time and other factors beyond the control of the researcher.

Review of Literature

Study by Koch et.al (2019) evaluated the effectiveness of dance movement therapy(DMT) and dance interventions for psychological health outcomes of a sample size of 2,374. The findings of his longitudinal study suggested that DMT decreases depression and anxiety and increases quality of life and interpersonal and cognitive skills, whereas dance interventions increase (psycho-)motor skills. This meta-analysis highlights the potential of DMT and dance interventions as an effective complementary treatment for various psychological and physical health conditions.

A descriptive research on Impact of Indian Classical Dance on Physical & Mental Health by BalajiDeekshitulu(2019) emphasized that body and mind are interrelated; therefore suggested that the diverse Indian dance styles can be used for therapeutic purposes. The study further mentions through the lens of Ayurveda that the benefits of sangeet (singing, dance, and music) cannot be undermined. Strong dancing styles like Bhangara promote health and strength. Anger and anxiety can be released with the help of Kathak dance's rapid footwork. Manipuri dancers use circular motions thus aiding flexibility of the body.

Many researches have been undertaken on the effects of dance/movement therapy in special settings with physical problems such as amputations, traumatic brain injury and stroke, chronic illnesses such as anorexia, bulimia, cancer, Alzheimer's disease, cystic fibrosis, heart disease, diabetes, asthma, AIDS, and arthritis. The findings have generally been found to be very positive (Chrisman, 2001; Boughton, 2002; Byers et al., 2002).

According to Chrisman's definition "Dance is the most fundamental human behaviour and art form, involving direct expression through the body. Thus, it is an intimate and powerful medium for therapy based on the assumption that body and mind are interrelated. For centuries people of many cultures have used dance to express powerful emotions, tell stories, treat illnesses, celebrate important events, and maintain communal bonds". (Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention, Vol. 6, 2005 409 Dance for Cancer Prevention)

The American Dance Therapy Association (ADTA) defines dance/ movement therapy as the psychotherapeutic use of dance and movement in a creative process, which improves the individuals' physical, emotional, cognitive as well as social integration. Important factors are the body, the dance, creativity and the therapeutic relationship (Jordan, 2003).

Chronological development of Dance Therapy is a significant method to understand how DMT has been recognized and evolved over the years as more and more evidence was available about its therapeutic effects on the mind and body.

The therapeutic aspect of dance has always been valued by people of different cultures. Especially, among the religiously motivated, original societies therapeutic value of dance is unquestionably accepted. The curable Shamandances, "trans dances" and "ritual dances" of these societies are some of the examples. However, effects of these dances were and still are more spiritual than physical.

Importance of dance therapy, as a curable physical activity, was not known until the Middle Ages. It was first mentioned around sixteenth century in Robert Burton's "Anatomy of melancholy." The English physician suggested dance as a therapy for treatment of melancholic behaviour; the second part of the book lists several genres of cures in which dance is widely mentioned as a therapeutic use of exercise, both physical and spiritual. A century later another British author, Richard Browne in his "Medicina musica" first published in 1727, recommended dance as being the most effective of all forms of exercise (Arcangeli, 2000).

Dance anthropologist Paul Spencer, the editor of "Society and the Dance", also widely mentions about dance therapy saying that the notion that dancing may have some therapeutic value is at least as ancient as the dancing epidemics of the Middle Ages. "Literature on dance frequently emphasizes its cathartic value, releasing pent-up emotions. This notion was developed in stages in the writings of Herbert Spencer when he explored the variety of emotions that expressed themselves in muscular action, first in relation to his genius theory of the origins of music (1857), then of laughter (1860), and then briefly of dancing (1862:234-5)

He opined that emotions are a form of nervous energy that become intensified when denied its natural outlet, and had to be released through some other channel. This concept of dancing as a safety valve for releasing pent-up emotions foreshadowed Freud's concept of the libido- a psychic force analogous to hunger that requires some direct or indirect physical outlet" (Spencer, 1985).

Dance conditions an individual to moderate, eliminate, or avoid tension, chronic fatigue, and other disabling conditions that result from the effects of stress (Hanna, 1995).

The purpose of dance therapy is to help people achieve greater self-awareness and a positive sense of well-being.

The idea is that through authentic movement, one can express oneself and come into contact with the conscious and unconscious parts of their personality. This contact leads to accepting one's self for who they are (Jordan, 2003).

Thulin K, (1997). When words are not enough: dance therapy as a method of treatment for patients with psychosomatic disorders. (Am J Dance Therapy, 19, 25-43).

Moving rhythmically eases muscular rigidity, diminishes anxiety, and increases energy. The rhythmic beat, singing, and movement are therapeutic tools; through these, sick and depressed people find energy in their minds and bodies and smiles on their faces. Hope and positive thinking is created and helps people cope with their illness (Berrol, 1997; Boughton, 2002).

Content Analysis

The review of literature presents a very obvious reason to believe that dance movement, per se, definitely impacts mind and body in a positive manner. Given the fact that dance has the capacity to alleviate stress, marginalize trauma, improve immunity and foster a sense of well-being, this can be considered as a supplementary means of therapy to patients suffering from stress, depression, post-traumatic stress disorders, life threatening medical ailments, etc. All kinds of stresses, negative thought processes, etc., can actually aggravate the existing condition of those unwell.

Dance Movement can act as a significant distraction as the person can get carried away by the musical beats and the accompanied mind and body coordination that is needed while dancing. Dancing not only involves listening to the beats but also moving in sync with those beats. This can actually become quite a meditative state for the person dancing. And this is what helps in alleviating painful and bottled-up emotions and allowing them to fade away, thus bringing about a sense of calm and lightness for the dancer.

It is interesting to note that Universities, Institutions and some health care facilities in India have begun to underscore the importance of DMT and are also offering year-long courses for those interested in becoming Dance Movement Therapists. HSNC University, Mumbai, being a young University has adopted modern curriculum framework as per New Education Policy, (NEP) 2020 and has implemented incorporation of Performing Art Therapy including Music and Dance Movement Therapy as part of its BPA and MPA programmes.

Some handful hospitals and centers in India that offer dance movement therapy (DMT) include: Fortis Healthcare, SRCC, KidsCarePaediatric Neurology Centre.

Here it can be seen that DMT as a supplementary therapy method is yet to become a

commonly accepted form of therapy. Although courses are being offered for people to choose DMT as their professions, it is still not a widely acknowledged or accepted line of therapy. Lack of awareness about the therapeutic/ healing effect of dance on the mind and body is yet to gain ground. Societal acknowledgment of those with special needs, or those with any kind of mental or psychological disorders requiring an alternate form of therapy is still quite underrated fact in the Indian context. More the awareness about DMT providing a healing with no medicines involved, better will be the scope for Dance Movement Therapists to prove themselves in treating patients with psychological disorders, cancers, terminally ill patients (who are capable of physical movement), and so on.

Challenges

- To create enough awareness and confidence amongst people about choosing DMT is a major challenge.
- Societal acceptance that mental illnesses and ailments are a kind of treatable issues, in the first place, rather than something that needs to be ridiculed about.
- Apart from that opposition could come from the Pharma companies as DMT would mean lesser consumption of medicines and a dominant reliance of a section of patients on DMT to heal them and live a healthier life.

Conclusion

Dance, as a form of therapy does not only helps people with chronic illnesses; it also, helps socially and physically abused people to cope with their emotion, anger and frustration. The literature reviewed shares light on the fact that DMT can actually transform the way society looks at treating various illnesses and that too in a more pleasurable manner. The after effect of dancing is always a gentle behaviour, calmness and clear thinking. With better awareness about the positive impact of DMT, increasing number of hospitals and other health care facilities will adopt DMT in their routine functioning. Thus creating a medicine-free (oral or injectibles) way of treatment for those who would benefit out of it.

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